

A FURTHER REPORT OF CASES OF INFLAMMATORY AFFECTIONS OF THE LABYRINTH.*

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On January 10, 1913, in conjunction with Drs. Fowler, Kopetzky and Sharp, I had the pleasure of reporting twenty cases of labyrinthine affections before the Sections on Otology of the New York Academy of Medicine.

Since that date a series of six cases have occurred in my various services, this series including one private case of Dr. J. J. Thomson and one of Dr. J. C. Sharp. In the former series the diagnosis and treatment of the cases was given in full without comment or conclusions. The same rule is followed in the present series, it being my belief that there are certain points in the management of purulent labyrinthitis that can only be settled upon a basis of an extended series of cases.

I take this occasion to suggest to the members of this society that they keep careful notes of every case and report them in full, especially autopsy data whenever it can be secured.

Case 1: S. Z., male, aged 52, seen for the first time September 9, 1913. Nine years ago abscess in right ear. Discharge began without pain, has continued since then, and has always been foul. Eight weeks ago attacks of vertigo in the mornings. Attacks increased in severity and four weeks ago nausea and vomiting with each attack accompanied by severe headache on right side. He was compelled to remain in bed, unable to raise his head without vertigo, nausea and vomiting. For the past two weeks he has felt better and has been up and about again; complains now of slight unsteadiness in his gait, and headache. During the attack four weeks ago he had fever and has lost considerable weight. He does not remember when he had hearing in his right ear; mind clear; recognizes and can name objects presented to him. Pupils are equal and react promptly to light; knee jerks increased; no ataxia in arms or legs; no spontaneous pointing error; no *adiadochokinesis*; no paresis arms or legs.

Functional examination: Right ear, total deafness, (noise apparatus). Spontaneous rotatory nystagmus to both sides, more

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marked to left (sound side). Patient has tendency to fall to the right irrespective of the position of the head.

Rotation to right, nystagmus 17 degrees—probably compensation nystagmus. Rotation to left, nystagmus 18 degrees. Caloric, right negative.

Caloric, left rotation nystagmus. Right lasting $2\frac{1}{2}$ minutes (not prolonged). Fistula test negative.

Operation: Radical mastoid operation and drainage of labyrinth (September 12, 1913).

Large cholesteatoma which had eroded tegmen of the attic aditus and antrum was discovered. Large exposure of dura middle fossa which was covered with cholesteatoma, matrix and granulations. Large irregular fistula in external semi-circular canal; oval window does not contain stapes.

Post-operative: Pulse 70-80. Temperature 99.6° - 100.8° . Headache persists, but patient appears better. Slight facial paralysis.

September 30. Headache persists. Pulse, temperature, eyes, normal. Appetite fair. Plastic with closure of posterior wound. Considerable gain in weight.

October 7. Very little headache. Temperature, pulse, eye grounds normal.

October 10. Patient left hospital. Condition good. Feels well. Radical cavity not completely epidermatized. For almost a month patient gained in weight, felt well, grew gradually stronger, and was considering his return to his work, but he did complain of more or less persistent headache, all other localizing signs being absent.

November 6. Suddenly intense headache, vertigo, nausea, followed by high fever and persistent vomiting. Re-admitted to the hospital. Temperature 103° , pulse, 86, head retracted, neck rigid, cervical vertebrae tender, pupils sluggish, knee jerks increased, Kernig positive, delirium. Cerebro-spinal fluid turbid, contains many leucocytes and cocci. The same night, chiefly for the reason that his headache had invariably been located in the temporal region, extending to the outer angle of the orbit, I decided to explore that region first. The same night I evacuated a large temporo-sphenoidal abscess; pus green and very foul. After evacuation of abscess, pulse 120. Death in twenty-four hours from diffuse purulent meningitis. No autopsy could be obtained.

Case 2: S. T., male, aged 24 years, admitted to the Manhattan Eye, Ear and Throat Hospital September 16, 1913.

Chronic purulent otitis media, right, for past twelve years. Discharge moderate in amount, and at intervals ceased entirely. Gen-

eral health good. Wassermann negative. One month ago cold and earache for two days accompanied by an increase in the discharge. Felt suddenly faint after a few moments, vertigo and vomiting which occurred at intervals for two days. Thereafter he experienced vertigo whenever the eyes were rotated to the side; vertigo also when stooping. He had an attack two days ago but at present is not dizzy.

Functional examination: Voice right, 8 feet. Voice left, 2 feet. Weber to right, Rinne both negative. Spontaneous nystagmus toward both sides about equal. Turning to right, nystagmus 16 degrees. Turning to left, nystagmus 21 degrees. Fistula test positive.

Operation: Radical mastoid operation. Large fistula in the anterior limb of external semi-circular canal. Following operation, partial facial paralysis. Hearing present, no increase in the spontaneous nystagmus. September 23, condition unchanged. No vertigo. September 30, plastic with suture of posterior wound. January 17, 1914, hearing present, whisper at few inches. Rotation to right, nystagmus 23 degrees. Rotation to left, nystagmus 29 degrees. Caloric positive. Fistula test negative. Facial paralysis subsiding.

Case 3: E. C., female, aged 10 years, Dr. Sharp's patient. Chronic purulent otitis media, right, since infancy. Discharge rather profuse and foul. No tenderness of mastoid, no edema, fundus full of granulations.

Functional tests: Right ear, hearing totally destroyed, (noise apparatus). Caloric positive. Fistula test negative.

Operation: April 16, 1914, radical mastoid operation was performed by Dr. Sharp in the Manhattan Eye, Ear and Throat Hospital. No fistula in the labyrinthine capsule. Cavity not yet epidermatized. Hearing entirely destroyed.

Case 4: E. S., male, aged —, admitted to the Manhattan Eye, Ear and Throat Hospital, January 28, 1914. Dr. Kopetzky had charge of the case.

Family history negative. Previous history: Has always been well and strong. At 8 years of age was operated upon for a "swelling" behind the right ear. This ear was re-operated upon when he was 16 years old. Since that time the ear has discharged constantly but not profusely. For the past few days slight headache. Patient presents a partly epidermatized radical cavity. Inner tympanic wall contains few granulations. Some discharge. No tenderness.

Functional tests: Left ear hearing normal. Right ear total deafness, (noise apparatus). Caloric positive. Weber to left. Schwabach right shortened. Rinne right negative ad infinity. Spontaneous nystagmus to both sides more marked to left. No Romberg or ataxia. Rotation to right, 20 degrees. Compensation. Rotation to right nystagmus 18 degrees. Caloric right negative. Weber to left. Fistula test negative.

Secondary radical operation by Dr. Kopetsky. In the region of the tube, granulations and polypi. The inner tympanic wall consisted of dense, newly formed bone which had obliterated the foramen ovale, the foramen rotundum and the entire labyrinth. Small exposure of sinus. Plastic and suture. The radical cavity is now completely epidermatized.

Case 5: Case of labyrinthine fistula. I am permitted to report this case through the courtesy of Dr. J. J. Thomson.

M. C., female, aged 18 years, was seen for the first time January 16, 1914, and gave the following history: She has always been a healthy girl, and with the exception of measles, chickenpox and whooping cough, has not suffered from any of the usual diseases of childhood. She stated positively that until six weeks previously, she had never had any trouble with her ears. Her father and mother, in spite of repeated questioning, also were positive that she had never had discharge or even an earache. No family or personal history of tuberculosis could be obtained.

Six weeks ago she had a severe cold followed by acute otitis media in the left ear. The drum ruptured spontaneously and the ear has discharged profusely since. She has not had any marked pain since the rupture of the drum, but the mastoid has been tender at times for the past four weeks. She has had tinnitus and defective hearing in the left ear since the beginning of the otitis. The day before her visit to me, she noticed that she was a little dizzy when she turned her head rapidly, and the morning of January 16 was more so, but was able to be about, and only felt dizzy when she turned her head. She had not vomited or felt nauseated.

Examination: The drum could not be seen, on account of narrowing of the canal at the fundus. There was what appeared to be a granulation at the bottom of the canal. There was a moderate amount of discharge not very malodorous, culture from which grew staphylococcus aureus only. The mastoid was very tender, but not swollen. Temperature was 99.4°, and pulse 88. There was hearing in the left ear, but only a loud voice could be heard, and she

lateralized the Weber to the left ear. The caloric test was negative, but I think this was due to our inability to get the water far enough into the canal. There was a very marked positive fistula test. Compression would cause a rotatory nystagmus toward the diseased ear which would last for several minutes. There was no spontaneous nystagmus.

The following day the same tests were made and gave the same result. All the symptoms were the same. It was decided to wait a few days before doing any operative procedure, on account of the recent onset of the dizziness. January 18 she vomited a few times and felt nauseated a good deal, and said for the first time that she felt dizzy while lying quietly in bed. There was also a slight spontaneous nystagmus toward the good ear.

Operation: The mastoid cortex was removed with the rongeur without the use of a chisel to avoid jarring. On its removal, a whitish membrane presented in the cavity which resembled somewhat the lateral sinus, but while we were observing it, pus began to exude from beneath it under pressure, and it proved to be a membrane enclosing about two drachms of pus and granulations. Culture from pus did not grow any bacteria. This was a large perisinus abscess. A radical operation was done. The incus was not seen, but the bleeding was so profuse that I could not tell positively that it was not removed without being observed. A portion of the malleus was recovered, and the stapes was seen in place. There was a large fistula in the horizontal semi-circular canal, occupying the position of the maximum of its convexity. This fistula was covered by a pad of granulations.

The evening of the operation there was no change in the nystagmus. It was still directed to the sound ear and was apparent on the slightest rotation to the right, but not when the patient looked directly ahead. During the next twenty-four hours the patient was comfortable, there was no dizziness or nausea, nor rise in temperature.

January 21. Patient is feeling well, has good appetite, has not been dizzy and temperature is normal. The spontaneous nystagmus is less marked than before operation but is still present, and is directed toward the sound ear. In the Weber test the sound of the fork is heard in the operated ear. January 23. First dressing. Wound is clean, temperature normal, no dizziness, and the spontaneous nystagmus has disappeared. Weber lateralized to the operated ear. Patient is allowed to sit up. January 31. Plastic oper-

ation performed. Posterior wound closed. Stitches became infected in the lower part of posterior wound. Wound opened. February 16. Wound doing well. Middle ear epidermidalized. February 25. Wound entirely healed and patient discharged. Hearing distance for the whisper in the operated ear is 20 feet.

Case 6: Report of a case of suppurative labyrinthitis. This case came to Dr. Phillips' Clinic at the Manhattan Eye and Ear Hospital April 5, 1913. He gave a history of dizziness for about two weeks. He had chronic suppuration for a great many years in both ears. Both ears were discharging slightly at examination. Patient did not complain of anything but dizziness and deafness. Tests: Hearing in both ears tested with noise apparatus. Very little hearing in right ear. Rotation to right, nystagmus to left for 14 seconds. Rotation to left, nystagmus to right for 9 seconds. Caloric test negative in right ear, not used in left. Patient sent to hospital. A few days later he complained of severe headache, and had a temperature of 100°. Neither mastoids were tender, and the discharge was less in each ear. Tongue coated and remained so in spite of free catharsis. The severe headache continued for a week, the patient was rational, memory good, eye-grounds clear, temperature from 100° to 102°. Pulse gradually became slower until it was 60, but at times it would go to 88. No retraction of head, dizziness disappeared, headache improved after ten days, but returned. Leucocytosis count negative; headache, variable, but usually present, localized to the left side. No vomiting. Patient gave a history of syphilis, and has old cutaneous lesions. Wassermann was negative.

Examination on April 18 showed very little change. Patient rational and clear. Memory good. No pain or percussion of head. No mastoid tenderness. No dizziness. Nystagmus spontaneous to the left. Hearing for watch apparently present in right ear. Hearing in left. No restlessness. Headache still present. Tongue coated. Temperature 102°. Had a chill in the morning. Exploration of the cerebellum the following day. Decided on anti-syphilitic treatment. Also ordered spinal puncture. Examination of fluid showed it to be loaded with streptococcus mucosa. Chemical tests showed excess of lactic acid, absence of copper reducing agent. Patient almost unconscious. Facial paralysis present. Condition very bad. Operation, drainage of cisterna magna. Cerebellum directly under dura. Only small amount of fluid escaped. Patient died same night.

Autopsy: Mastoid filled with pus—purulent labyrinthitis—meningitis—no abscess. Autopsy of head only permitted. Removal

of the cranial vault showed the dura very adherent to the bone throughout its extent. The meninges tissues thickened—evidence of a chronic inflammatory process presented.

The opened meninges revealed a large collection of thin fluid in the meshes of the pia. The largest collection of this fluid was found in the posterior cranial fossa. The membranes at the base of the brain generally were more acutely inflamed than elsewhere.

Upon removing the brain, a rather distinct collection of whitish pus—in contrast with the other collections of fluid found—was localized at the internal auditory meatus, filling this structure and bathing the facial and the auditory nerves. The removal of the adherent meninges from the bone on the internal side of the petrosa, disclosed darkly discolored bone, involving the tegmen tympani, and tegmen cellulae mastoidea.

Opening the tegmen in these regions, we found the tympanic cavity filled with purulent contents, semi-fluid in nature. The malleus was recovered and found to present no evidence of necrosis. The incus was not found. The removal of the tegmen cellulae mastoidea revealed the mastoid process filled with dark, discolored, thick, but semi-fluid mass—some intra-cellular walls were present, but the probe easily broke down these evidences of an acute infection of the mastoid process.

Opening inward into the cochlea from the internal auditory meatus, we found this structure likewise filled with similar purulent matter, the only anatomical structure intact being the promontory. The superior semi-circular canal was likewise discolored. The lateral sinus on the right side contained a red thrombus—probably a post-mortem condition.

Brain: Pial vessels injected. Both lateral ventricles much distended with a water-clear fluid. Incision into two sections of both the cerebrum and the cerebellum failed to reveal any abscesses.

COMMENTS ON AUTOPSY FINDINGS.

The Autopsy findings warrant the following conclusions:

1. The patient suffered from an old, chronic meningeal inflammation. His admission of having had syphilis would explain this finding, in spite of the negative report of the Wassermann.

2. There was an acute exacerbation or an acute infection of the middle ear and the labyrinth cavities. The intact malleus, with its ligament attachments, speaks against a chronic middle-ear infection. The bacterial finding also speaks against a chronic otitis media. The acute infections involved the middle ear, including the

mastoid process, and the labyrinth, finally breaking endo-cranially along the route of the nerves, facial and auditory, to begin the infection of the meninges at the internal auditory meatus.

3. The infection resulted in a general involvement of the basilar meninges, and the accumulation of purulent fluid in the posterior cranial fossa—a posterior basilar meningitis resulting. The distension of the lateral ventricles by water-clear fluid was a secondary manifestation.

4. The facial paralysis noted as presenting itself on April 19, just prior to operative intervention of the meninges, is accounted for by the route travelled by the infection from the internal ear to the meninges.

5. The operation for the drainage of the cisterna magna was not successful, in so far that there was present at autopsy a very large collection of pus in the posterior cranial fossa, which was not drained off by the procedure, although this opening did not sufficiently divide the foramen magnum from the internal side.

(Note). There is no way of telling whether this accumulation of fluid in the posterior cranial fossa was an artifact of post-mortem incident, or not. Certainly at the time of operation there was no such collection of fluid present, as the cerebellum presented itself immediately upon incision of the dura.

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Surgical Treatment of Post-operative Palate Defects. G. V. I. BROWN, *Jour. A. M. A.*, May 16, 1914, p. 1539.

For successful closing of palatal defects, their underlying factors must be discovered and corrected. If a second operation be necessary it should only be performed after nine months or a year. Patients who have been operated on in early infancy by compression or a forcing together of the maxillary bones with silver wire and lead plates present the most difficult post-operative defects. They have nasal defects, histories of middle-ear and mastoid disease, deformities of mouth due to contracted palates, and loss of tooth-germs due to destruction when inserting wires. ED.